

CLOUD BASED SECURITY CENTRALIZED DATABASE FOR STORAGE OF VOTER'S INFORMATION USING CRYPTOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE

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Abstract— Network Security is the most vital component in information security because it is responsible for securing all information passed through networked computers. Cloud is an Internet-based computing technology, where shared resources such as software, platform, storage and information are provided to customers on demand. Cloud Computing is a computing platform for sharing resources that include infrastructures, software, applications, and business processes. Cloud Computing is a virtual pool of computing resources. It provides computing resources in the pool for users through internet, Cloud computing as an emerging computing paradigm aims to share storage, computation and services transparently among massive users. Current Cloud computing systems poses serious limitation in protecting users' data confidentiality. Since users' sensitive data is presented in unencrypted forms to remote machines owned and operated by third party service providers, the risks of unauthorized disclosure of the users' sensitive data by service providers may be quite high. There are many techniques for protecting users' data from outside attackers. An approach is presented to protecting the confidentiality of users' data from service providers, and ensures service providers cannot collect users' confidential data while the data is processed and stored in Cloud computing systems. Cloud computing systems provide various internet based data storage and services. Due to its many major benefits, including cost effectiveness and high scalability and flexibility, Cloud computing is gaining significant momentum recently as a new paradigm of distributed computing for various applications, especially for business applications along with the rapid growth of the Internet. With the rise of the era of "Cloud computing", concerns about "Internet Security" continue to increase. Cryptography, together with suitable communication protocols, can provide a high degree of protection in digital communications against intruder attacks as far as the communication between two different computers is concerned.

Key Words — Cryptography, Biometrics, Algorithm, Cloud, E-Voting, Database.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cryptography is a vital of today's computer and communications networks, protecting everything from business e-mail to bank transactions and internet shopping. While classical and modern cryptography employ various mathematical techniques to avoid eavesdroppers from learning the contents of encrypted messages. Computer systems and networks which are storing, processing and communicating sensitive or valuable information require protection against such unauthorized access[1]. In wireless networks, the security of data is an important aspect and encryption algorithms play an important role to provide the security to the wireless networks. The main aim of the cryptography is to enhance the data confidentiality and privacy by making the information unintelligible. Hence the data cannot be interrupted by the intruders. The Encryption techniques and various algorithms are used to provide the needed security to the applications. This paper provides a fair performance comparison between the various cryptography algorithms such as the AES, RSA, RC2, DES, 3DES, DSA where both types of symmetric and asymmetric techniques. The demand for the ubiquitous personal communications is driving the development of new networking techniques. In the wireless communication the security of the data plays the vital role. To improve the security of the data being

transmitted various techniques are employed. The important method used to provide the confidentiality is the data encryption and decryption technique. Network security becomes more crucial when the volume of the data becomes larger and complex. Cryptography is the art of transforming the information's on the applications into scrambled or in unintelligible format. It relates to the study of mathematical techniques related to the aspects of information security such as the confidentiality, data integrity, and authentication of the data. The technology used for this is called as the cryptology. When the user defined input may in any of the format such as the text, or an image is which is plain, is converted into a scrambled form called as the cipher text or cipher image. This process is referred to us as encryption. To convert the data the user should provide the specific algorithm. The reversible process in which the original data is recovered is called as the decryption process. In cryptography majorly three types of encryption techniques are taken place. The substitution technique, the transposition technique and the transposition- substitution technique. The most important type of the encryption type is the symmetric key encryption. In the symmetric key encryption both for the encryption and decryption process the same key is used. Hence the secrecy of the key is maintained and it is kept private. It works with high speed. The symmetric key encryption takes place in two methodologies either as the block ciphers or as the stream ciphers. One of the main advantages of using the symmetric key encryption is that the computational power to this encryption technique is small [1]

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Models for Internet Voting Systems

There are basically three models often used in internet voting systems and these include the following [2];

1. Blind signature: This method involves the voter attaining a token blindly endorsed only by the professional. Then voter forwards vote secretly along with the token as eligibility proof. Structures built on

blind signatures commonly use unsigned medium so as to forward the un-blinded signature and the encrypted vote to an election specialist, guaranteeing the concealment of the source [2].

2. Homomorphism: It is a model which involves the tally process being subjected to encryption of votes where addition and multiplication is performed homomorphically on to the cast votes to be able to come up with results. It is a technique which conceals the ballot content via an unrestricted channel and the ballots are decrypted by a pair of authorized persons [2].
3. Mix-nets Model: This model involves linking numerous servers known as mixes which enable randomization of the messages entered and produces transformed messages. Both the input and output messages are indifferent hence providing anonymity for voters [3].

B. Cloud Computing and Cloud Services

The Cloud computing is the communication network or a network which is Combined with computing infrastructure. Cloud computing system is accessed using network which provides software, hardware, processing power etc. to the user when demand is generated. Cloud Computing is a virtual pool of computing resources which provides the pool to users through internet.

Cloud Computing provides various services to user by creating group of clusters and grids of computers [4]. The main goal behind this is to provide services in virtualized manner to reduce burden of user to maintain everything by itself. It also refers to the web-based computing which provides devices with shared pool of resources, information or software on demand and pay per-use basis. Instead of having local servers or own devices to manage applications, people use sharing computing resources model of Cloud. The Cloud computing provides environment in which user can have its own virtual infrastructure using which they can perform tasks without depending on geographical boundary. Because of the flexible environment and cheaper cost, people are attracted

towards the use of Cloud services that may be related to Platform, software or infrastructure. Based on the usage of Cloud, there are three deployment models: Public Cloud, Private Cloud and Hybrid Cloud.

The Cloud computing provides a numerous advantages to its users but at the dark side it's also suffers from lots of issues like Integrity or Storage Correctness, Availability, Confidentiality and more. These issues make the adaption of cloud environment somewhat difficult for the users [5]. Therefore lots of research is required in this direction to set a trust of Cloud user on Cloud service providers.

Cloud provides four types of services based on different requirements of clients as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Cloud Services [6]

C. Cloud Models

Cloud provides three types of models: Public Cloud which is open for all; Private Cloud where access is only permitted to the user who are the user of that private area; Hybrid cloud which is performing compromise task of both types of services provided by public and private Cloud.

There are four deployment models [7] which are defined as follows:

1). *Private Cloud*: Clouds implementing this deployment model are intended to be used by a single organization. It is owned and managed by organization itself, or a third party responsible to provision of private cloud services. Generally, private clouds offer better quality of service. However, they require significant investment and management effort.

2). *Community cloud*: Some organizations may have shared concerns and similar requirements. These organizations may benefit from deploying shared cloud environment that is managed by one or more attending organizations, a third party, or their combination. Community cloud may be a good choice for the organizations with moderate finances and requiring partially manageable cloud services, at lower cost.

3). *Public Cloud*: This type of cloud environments are provided to the general public. Multiple customers may share the public cloud, which results in lower service costs for the individual consumer. However, customers have less control over the cloud infrastructure in comparison with private and community clouds. Additionally, data is shared with unknown parties in a physical level. This consideration should be taken into account, before storing sensitive data in public cloud.

4). *Hybrid Cloud*: Hybrid clouds are the composition of multiple cloud infrastructures bound together by certain technology, enabling interoperability between cloud services. Hybrid clouds can consist of private, public and community cloud infrastructures.

Public cloud is a most demanding deployment model, since it provides most significant and beneficial features of cloud, such as lower costs, extensive computing power, rapid scalability, etc.

D. Security and Privacy Requirements in Cloud Computing

Protection of data is an important requirement while designing IT infrastructure of the organization. These requirements get even more stringent when data moves to cloud, and data becomes accessible through Internet. Therefore, strong authentication and access control mechanisms should be in place while deploying such systems.

- **Authenticity of Data**: Data stored in cloud should be authentic, which means it should be possible to determine if the data is genuine and to verify the creator or owner of the data [8]. Deceptive data might result in unpredictable consequences, depending on use case scenario. Therefore, it should be possible to determine the owner of the data for further investigation. Note that owner or creator of the data

may be a group or certain set of users. Authenticity of the data might be achieved by various signature schemes [8].

- **Authentication:** Authentication of users and components is a crucial part of the collaboration in cloud. Data should be accessed only by the legitimate users. Therefore, all users are required to perform authentication process and getting authorized by the system, before allowing them to perform any other operations. Unauthorized access to the data might result in information leakages, data manipulation and other undesirable consequences [8].
- **Non-repudiation:** Changing or deleting any valuable data might have significant consequences and result in money and reputation losses. Collaboration in cloud may deal with data provided by various data providers, and inconsistencies in these data might lead to reputation and money losses of data providers. Inconsistencies might occur by the ill-intentioned actions of the users and other involved parties. Non-repudiation property ensures that users cannot deny their transactions and actions on datasets [9], and will carry responsibility over them.
- **Integrity:** Collaboration in cloud may require large amount of data to be processed. Therefore, accuracy and consistency of processed data as well as obtained results should be preserved [8]. Inconsistencies of the stored data might result in unpredictable consequences, depending on use case. For example, integrity violations may result in large amount of re-computations, and in wrong outcomes, which is unacceptable risk in some cases (e.g. healthcare systems).
- **Confidentiality:** Unauthorized insiders or systems should not have permissions and ability to access data, which may be considered as an internal document, trade secrets, intellectual property, etc. In the cloud computing environment data is distributed over the remote servers that are shared with others and can be accessed through Internet or other connections.

Moreover, collaboration might involve multiple cloud providers in business [9]. These factors will increase the threat of data compromise in the cloud, since increased or even unknown number of access points will be available to the sensitive data [10]. Therefore, serious confidentiality considerations should be taken into account, before moving data into the cloud. It is possible to achieve confidentiality through encryption mechanisms [8]. However, in most of the cases data should still be searchable in order to process queries on datasets and to support certain activities [11]. Techniques like searchable encryption or maintaining index of data might help in this case. Additionally confidentiality should be preserved while transporting the data [10], therefore encrypted channels like TLS, VPNs, etc. should be considered.

- **Availability:** Users of a cloud should be able to access and use needed data resources on demand. High availability should be achieved, by preventing situations, such as Denial-of-Service attacks, power outages and hardware failures [11]. Since cloud provides extensive processing power, organizations may perform their data analysis more faster and effectively using cloud resources. However, analysis of data might suffer from unavailability of the data resources needed for analysis on demand.
- **Auditability:** Audit procedures should be in place, in order to maintain log of every access and modification of data in distributed environment [9]. Security breach notifications might be generated automatically based on logs. Audit logs might be stored and managed decentrally, however, it should be possible to reconstruct prior state of information and replay performed actions by combining relevant logs together. Audit logs might be the only way to track changes in the datasets. Additionally, confidentiality, integrity and availability of audit logs must be ensured.

- **Backup Procedures:** All data stored in the cloud system should be backed up, in order to prevent data losses. Cloud service providers establish backup procedures to their customers as an indistinguishable part of their service. However, it might be risky to allow the cloud service providers to back up sensitive data and store it in distributed environment [9]. Even if built-in backup procedure is one of the benefits of cloud service, it might have a negative effect when sensitive data is considered.
- **Data Location Restrictions:** Data in the cloud is stored in the distributed manner, in the servers located all over the world. There is a need to restrict locations where cloud service provider will physically host the data [12], before storing data or deploying corporative systems in the cloud. It is reasonable to avoid countries where intellectual property and privacy laws are inadequate and where data may be a subject of investigation due to the intrusive nature of the government.
- **Data Traceability and Labeling:** All data stored in the cloud must be traceable in order to identify the origin of the leakage. Additionally, confidential data should be labeled, indicating that the data is proprietary and unauthorized usage of it will have legal consequences. These requirements are especially important in cloud environment, where increased vectors of information leakage present.
- **Data Segmentation:** Cloud computing benefits from resource sharing and virtualization mechanisms. That means multiple virtual machines are running on one physical machine and controlled by software hypervisor to keep appropriate separation of resources [12]. Cloud provides less separation than private IT infrastructures, where separate physical servers are deployed. So, there is a potential threat of data compromise through virtual machines running under others control on the same physical server where sensitive data of certain organizations might be stored. Also, there is a risk of the network traffic

capture in such cases. In ideal, data of separate parties should be processed and stored through unshared physical machines [13], which is not the conceptional idea of a cloud computing. Therefore resource sharing must be limited to the minimum, depending on the agreement with the cloud provider. It is worth to note that, due to the resource sharing between different organizations in the cloud, forensic inspections of the storage will be a legal challenge.

E. Authentication Techniques in Cloud Computing

Considering the ever-increasing growth in the use of cloud services and the tendency of users to adopt this service, there is an increase in security threats for data storage in the cloud. The word cloud initially implied the storage of user data in a location provided by a third party. That is, information was not stored on the user's computer hard drive and it was stored elsewhere which was accessible at all times and in every place. The user was able to access the information at any location. Despite its numerous advantages, this method also has disadvantages. For instance, how would a company agree to store its sensitive information at a location other than its own storage devices, where the company does not know who can access the aforesaid information? That is why different threats and security mechanisms were developed [14]. As you know, in the majority of cases where security is breached, the goal is to destroy the confidentiality of information, data accuracy, and information accessibility. Given brute force attacks, the username and password mechanism was demonstrated to be poor more than ever. Organizations and people expect different security parameters to be employed for increasing the security of access to their sensitive information. With all the explanations provided, the first and most important step in the design of a system is its security. Cloud computing users should be authenticated to be able to use the resources. It is noteworthy that a great number of attacks occur at this entrance gate. Hence, the design of a secure mechanism to authenticate users is a substantial aid to increased security of the entire system. Different authentication methods in a cloud environment are described in this section. These

methods are typically employed to increase cloud security [14].

- **Biometric authentication:** Biometric authentication supports three factors of information security, namely authentication, identification, and non-repudiation. This mechanism is based upon the identification of physiological or behavioral characteristics of a person. In addition, it is a powerful authentication mechanism providing the factors “what we are” and “what we know.” Physical biometrics: Physical biometrics is a type of authentication based on physical characteristics of human. A major defect of physical biometrics pertains to circumstances where a great number of customers need to be authenticated at the same time. This reduces the speed of the mechanism. There are several physical biometric authentication techniques such as hand geometry recognition, fingerprint recognition, palm print recognition, voice recognition, face recognition, retinal scan, and iris scan. [15]. The biometric fingerprint and Election ID are used to ensure authenticity of a voter. Cryptography strengthens security of votes by encrypting the data using AES method. Visible text watermark is used to embed a text message on the candidate’s image to ensure integrity, and provide copyright protection of the images. The proposed e-voting system takes on an algorithm of $V_t = (E_i + B_f)$ where V_t represents vote, B_f stands for biometric fingerprint, and E_i represents Election ID. The system resolves issues related to security in terms of authenticity, integrity, and verifiability during elections. The proposed system has an Auto Count and Grading feature which automatically adds up the votes as soon as a vote is cast from any polling station and then the system grades the candidates accordingly in this regard, The research gap created by this work is that the system does not run on multiple platforms such as smart phones and cannot be accessed online.

The adoption of e-voting methods in electioneering processes will effectively reduce cost as well as enhance election activities [16]. What makes an e-voting model reliable and acceptable is its ability to properly authenticate voters and provide a secure means through which a voter can express his/her franchise. [16] therefore proposes a design of an e-voting system that leverages a Biometric Encryption scheme known as Biometric key Generation (BKG) which is a secured strategy that entails using of biometrics to generate secure cryptographic keys. The main objective of their research is to improve on the already existing E-voting systems adopting a secured bio-cryptographic technique vis Biometric key Generation (BKG) as well as using a secure transmission channel for confidential datasets of a voting process. The work developed a simulation model of an E-voting system which adopts relevant algorithms with emphasis on biometric key generation schemes.

[17] proposed a secured Cloud based E-Voting system using robust authentication. It is expected to make the election process low cost, systematic, transparent, efficient, fraud resistant and consequently make voters satisfied. The system will completely remove the duplicate and expired entries from central database server. The proposed voting system is deployable across the country. The proposed system is client/server architecture cloud based using web base, and a communication Technology, as a result voter can cast vote from anywhere. The propose system’s process contain three components that are Registration phase, Administration Phase and Vote casting phase. The security of the system is assured by the use of biometric fingerprint, iris authentication

III. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND DESIGN

The system design of this paper is divided into two main parts. They are the Database structure and the Cryptography using the Authentication Encryption System (AES).

A. Database Structure

Below is a Figure showing the Main menu of the e-Voting System where the structure of the Database was derived from and designed.

Figure 2: Main Menu used for the design of the System's Database

B. Database Development Tool

A relational database design was used to design the database. A relational database management system (RDBMS) is an excellent tool for organizing large amount of data and defining the relationship between the datasets in a consistent and understandable way. A RDBMS provides a structure which is flexible enough to accommodate almost any kind of data. Relationships between the tables were defined by creating special columns (keys), which contain the same set of values in each table. The tables can be joined in different combinations to extract the needed data. A RDBMS also offered flexibility that enabled redesign and regeneration of reports from the database without need to re-enter the data. Data dictionaries were used to provide definitions of the data used; these included the final data structures for the various tables and their corresponding data fields, description and sizes. The user application programs and interface were developed using PHP with support of Structured Query Language (SQL) and MySQL Database.

C. Cryptography – Math Specification

AES algorithm is based on AES key expansion to encrypt and decrypt data. It is another most important step in AES structure. Each round has a new key. The key expansion routine creates round keys word by word, where a word is an array of four bytes. The routine creates $4x(Nr+1)$ words. Where Nr is the number of rounds. The process is as follows:
The cipher key (initial key) is used to create the first four words. The size of key consists of 16 bytes (k_0 to k_{15}) that represents in an array. The first four bytes (k_0 to k_3) represents as w_0 , the next four bytes (k_4 to k_7) in first column represents as w_1 , and so on. We can use particular equation to calculate and find keys in each round easily as follows:

$$K[n]: w[i] = k[n-1]: w[i] \text{ XOR } k[n]: w[i] \dots\dots\dots 1$$

For w_0 we have to use particular equation that is different from above equation.

$$K[n]: w_0 = k[n-1]: w_0 \text{ XOR Sub Byte } (k[n-1]: w_3 \gg 8) \text{ XOR Rcon}[i] \dots\dots\dots 2$$

K1:

$$W_0 = 0f \ 15 \ 71 \ c9$$

$$W_1 = 47 \ d9 \ e8 \ 59$$

$$W_2 = 0c \ b7 \ ad \ e8$$

$$W_3 = af \ 7f \ 67 \ 98$$

How to find K_2 ?

$$K_2 = w_0 = k_1: w_0 \text{ XOR SubByte } (k_1:w_3 \gg 8) \text{ XOR Rcon}[2] \\ 0f \ 15 \ 71 \ c9 \text{ XOR Sub Byte } (af \ 7f \ 67 \ 98 \gg 8) \text{ XOR Rcon}[2]$$

$$\text{Rcon}[2] \text{ from Auxiliary function} = 02 \ 00 \ 00 \ 00$$

D. AES Algorithm

AES algorithm uses a particular structure to encrypt data to provide the best security as shown in Fig 3. To encrypt test, it relies on a number of rounds and inside each round comprise of four sub-processes. Each round consists of the following four steps to encrypt 128 bit block.

The first stage of each round starts with Sub Bytes transformation. This stage is depends on nonlinear S-box to substitute a byte in the state to another byte.

The next step after Sub Byte that performs on the state is Shift Row. The main idea behind this step is to shift bytes of the state cyclically to the left in each row rather than row number zero. In this process the bytes of row number zero remains and do not carry out any permutation. In the first row only one byte is shifted circular to left. The second row is shifted two bytes to the left. The last row is shifted three bytes to the left.

Another crucial step occurs of the state is Mix Column. The multiplication is carried out of the state. Each byte of one row in matrix transformation multiply by each value (byte) of the state column. In another word, each row of matrix transformation must multiply by each column of the state. The results of these multiplications are used with XOR to produce a new four bytes for the next state.

AddRoundKey is the most vital stage in AES algorithm. Both the key and the input data (also referred to as the state) are structured in a $4x4$ matrix of bytes. AddRoundKey has the ability to provide much more security during encrypting data. This operation is based on creating the relationship between the key and the cipher text. The cipher text is coming from the previous stage.

▪ **Algorithm for e-voting**

- i. procedure e-voting
- ii. Input: INEC database
- iii. Output: Election result
- iv. call procedure voters registration (database)
- v. while (voters !=null or election-time !=end) do
- vi. call procedure voter-authentication(thumb-impression)
- vii. call procedure vote-cast (voter)
- viii. call procedure e-voting
- ix. call procedure store-vote (vote)
- x. end while
- xi. call procedure announce-result (database, decryption-key)
- xii. end procedure

▪ **Algorithm for voters' registration**

1. procedure voters registration
2. Input: INEC database
3. Output: voters Register
4. while (voter != null) do // check if the voter has registered before
5. Ask user to place finger on biometric device and get the thumb impression
6. bimage1 = image IO. read (new finger template)
7. finger1 = set Finger Print Image (biamge1)
8. image1 = m-finger 1. get Finger Print Image Detail() . // store register voter data in database
9. insert into voters Table
10. end while
11. return INEC database
12. end procedure

▪ **Algorithm for voter-authentication**

1. procedure voter-authentication
2. Input: INEC database, voter data
3. Output: Boolean value // true for authentic voter and false for voter having fingerprint information
4. Ask voter to place finger on biometric device and get the thumb impression
5. nic=Tempinput.inputTempNumber()
6. ImageTest=imageResize(nic)
7. bimage1=image IO. read (ImageTest)
8. finger1=set Finger Print Image (biamge1)
9. finger2=get Image from INEC Database
10. mper= finger1.Match (finger1, finger2)
11. if (mper greater than 50) then match=true else match=false
12. end if
13. return match
14. end procedure

▪ **Algorithm for casing e-vote**

1. procedure casting e-vote
2. Input: voter information
3. Output: vote
4. if (voter authentication=true) then
5. showBallot()
6. select your choice
7. Review choice
8. while (choice=wrong) do
9. showBallot()
10. review choice again
11. choice=true

12. end while
13. end if
14. Encrypt (vote, pk) //The encrypted data are then transmitted to the server.
15. submit-vote()
16. return voter-choice
17. end procedure

E. Performance Evaluation

The software performance was tested using speed of data retrieval and security of the data protection. The security looks at the ability of the system to determine fraudulent users and deny them access to the system. The speed and security level obtained is as presented in the table below.

Technique Applied	Security Level	Speed
Cloud Database	93%	100Mb/s

Table 1: Performance Evaluation of the System

Fig. 3: AES Encryption / Decryption Algorithm

IV. CONCLUSION

Electoral system has been a major challenge to countries that practice the democratic system of government. With the advent of information technology, people are beginning to look the way of digitalizing the electoral system. So many countries have adopted e-voters registration system but are yet to adopt e-voting system. The fear is the concern for data security of the vote cast and the possibility of hacking the system database thereby falsifying the election result. So, this thesis developed a more secured e-voting system that can guarantee secured electronic voters registration, secured e-voting and secured vote collation and announcement. Electronic voting systems have many advantages over the traditional way of voting. Some of these advantages are lesser cost, faster tabulation of results, improved accessibility, greater accuracy, and lower risk of human and mechanical errors. It is very difficult to design ideal e-voting system which can allow security and privacy on the high level with no compromise. So this thesis provided the needed security by using biometric for voter authentication and fusing cryptography for data protection and security.

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